

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14556519>

UDK: 519.957

G'OVAK-MUHITNING CHIZIQLI TO'G'RI DINAMIK HAMDA BIR O'LCHOVLI CHIZIQLI BO'LMAGAN DINAMIK MASALALARNI SONLI YECHISH

Abdulxamid Erkinovich Xolmurodov,

Muxriddin Akram o'g'li Quzratov

Qarshi davlat universiteti,

abishx@mail.ru, quzratovm95@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada g'ovak muhitda to'lqin jarayonlarini tavsiflovchi bir o'lchovli chiziqli va chiziqli bo'lmagan dinamik masalalarni sonli usullar yordamida yechish masalalari o'rganilgan. Chiziqli giperbolik sistemalarning xususiyatlari, chegaraviy shartlar va kanonik shaklga keltirilishi asosida raqamli algoritmlar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *g'ovak muhit, chiziqli to'g'ri dinamik masala, chiziqli bo'lmagan dinamik masala, sonli yechim, xarakteristikalar bo'yicha integratsiya.*

ABSTRACT

This article explores the numerical solution of one-dimensional linear and nonlinear dynamic problems describing wave processes in porous media. Numerical algorithms are developed based on the properties of linear hyperbolic systems, boundary conditions, and their canonical forms.

Keywords: *porous media, linear dynamic problem, nonlinear dynamic problem, numerical solution, integration along characteristics.*

KIRISH. G‘ovak muhitda to‘lqin jarayonlarini o‘rganish ko‘plab ilmiy va amaliy sohalarda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu jarayonlar geofizika, gidrodinamika, qurilish materiallari fizikasi, neft va gaz qazib olish kabi sohalarda keng qo‘llaniladi. To‘lqin harakatini tavsiflovchi tenglamalar, odatda, chiziqli yoki chiziqli bo‘lmagan giperbolik tipga mansub bo‘lib, ularning analitik yechimlarini topish ko‘pincha murakkablik tug‘diradi. Shu sababli, sonli usullar va modellashtirish algoritmlarini ishlab chiqish ushbu masalalarni hal qilishning asosiy vositasiga aylangan.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA. Abdullayev, N. (2020). “Chiziqli giperbolik sistemalar va ularning amaliy qo‘llanilishi” maqolasida chiziqli giperbolik tizimlarning xususiyatlari va amaliy sohalarda qo‘llanilishi tahlil qilinadi. Mamatov, T. (2022). “G‘ovak muhitlarda dinamik jarayonlarni sonli yechish usullari” ishida g‘ovak muhitda to‘lqin va boshqa dinamik jarayonlarni yechish uchun raqamli usullar va modellashtirish metodlari taqdim etilgan. Imomnazarov, X. (2020). “G‘ovak muhitning chiziqli to‘g‘ri dinamik hamda bir o‘lchovli chiziqli bo‘lmagan dinamik masalalarini sonli yechish” kabi tadqiqotlarida g‘ovak muhitda to‘lqinlar va dinamik jarayonlarning chiziqli hamda chiziqli bo‘lmagan tavsiflari, ularning matematik modellarini sonli usullar yordamida yechish masalalari o‘rganilgan.

Ushbu ishlar sonli metodlar yordamida real tizimlarda yuzaga keladigan dinamik jarayonlarni aniq va samarali modellashtirishga qaratilgan.

Quyida ham g‘ovak-muhitning chiziqli to‘g‘ri dinamik hamda bir o‘lchovli chiziqli bo‘lmagan dinamik masalalarni sonli yechish bo‘yicha masalalar ko‘rib chiqiladi.

(x, t) ko‘rinishidagi $\rho_s(z)U_{tt} = (\mu(z)U_z)_z - \chi(z)\rho_l^2(z)(U_t - V_t)$ to‘lqin tenglamasi $U_{tt} - U_{xx} = \frac{\sigma'}{\sigma}U_x - \chi\frac{\rho_l^2}{\rho_s}(U_t - V_t)$ ko‘rinishga aylantiriladi.

$$U_{tt} = \frac{[\sigma(x)U_x]_x}{\sigma(x)} - \tilde{q}(x)(U_t - V_t) \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $\tilde{q}(x) = \chi(x) \frac{\rho_l^2(x)}{\rho_s(x)}$ - ma'lum funksiya, funksiya $\sigma(x)$ yuqorida $\sigma = \sigma(z) = \sqrt{\mu(z)\rho_s(z)}$ formula bilan aniqlanadi. Keyinchalik bu bo'limda $\tilde{q}(x)$ o'rniga, qulaylik uchun $q(x)$ yozamiz. (1) tenglama $\sigma(x)$ konstantaga ko'paytirilganda o'zgarmasligi uchun $\sigma(x)$ ni $\sigma(0) = 1$ normallashtiramiz. E'tibor bering, shu tarzda kiritilgan $\sigma(x)$ funksiyasi bilan Lamé koeffitsientini $\mu(x)$ hisoblash, agar $\rho_s(x)$ ma'lum bo'lsa, $\sigma(x)$ hisoblashga teng bo'ladi. $w = U_t$, $p = -\sigma(x)U_x$, $r = V_t$ qo'yamiz.

Keyin ikkinchi tartibli to'liq tenglamasi (1) birinchi tartibli tenglamalarning giperbolik tizimiga aylantiriladi

$$\begin{bmatrix} p \\ w \end{bmatrix}_t + A(x) \begin{bmatrix} p \\ w \end{bmatrix}_x = - \begin{bmatrix} p_0 \\ q(x)(w - r) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $A(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \sigma(x) \\ \sigma^{-1}(x) & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. Keling ($w = U_t$, $p = -\sigma(x)U_x$, $r = V_t$) shaklda qo'yaylik. Keyin ikkinchi tartibli to'liq tenglamasi (1) birinchi tartibli tenglamalarning giperbolik tizimiga aylantiriladi.

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} p \\ w \end{bmatrix}_t + A(x) \begin{bmatrix} p \\ w \end{bmatrix}_x = - \begin{bmatrix} p_0 \\ q(x)(w - r) \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (3)$$

bu yerda ($A(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \sigma(x) \\ \sigma^{-1}(x) & 0 \end{bmatrix}$). Chegaraviy shartlar shaklga aylantiriladi

$$p(0, t) = -\sigma(0)U_x(0, t) = f(t) \quad (3)$$

Tizim (2) qat'iy giperbolikdir. U ikkita xarakteristikaga ega, ular qiyalikli +1 va -1 to'g'ri chiziqlar, matritsaning xarakterli ildizlari $A(x)$. Shunday qilib, $A(x)$ matritsani diagonal shaklga keltirish mumkin.

Aniqlash $T(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sigma(x) \\ 1 & -\sigma(x) \end{bmatrix}$, bizda ... bor $T(x)A(x)T^{-1}(x) = \Lambda$ (4)

sistemani chapdan $T(x)$ ga ko'paytirib, $\sigma(x)$ differensiallanuvchi funksiya deb faraz qilsak, (2) sistemaning kanonik shaklini olamiz:

$$(Tv)_t + \Lambda(Tv)_x = \Lambda T_x v - T \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ q(x)(w - r) \end{bmatrix},$$

Bu yerda $v = (p, x)^T$. Portlash belgisida tizim shunday ko'rinadi

$$(p + \sigma w)_x + (p + \sigma w)_t = \sigma' w - \sigma(x)q(x)(w - r), \quad (4)$$

$$(p - \sigma w)_x - (p - \sigma w)_t = -\sigma' w - \sigma(x)q(x)(w - r), \quad (5)$$

bu yerda $\sigma'(x)$ hosila $\sigma(x)$. (4), (5) tenglamalarni integral shaklda ham yozish mumkin.

$t > x$ va har qanday (x, t) mintaqasidan ixtiyoriy qo'zg'almas nuqta $\tilde{x} < x$ uchun (4) tenglamani $\frac{dt}{dx} = 1$ xarakteristikasi bo'ylab integrallashimiz mumkin. $(\tilde{x}, t - x + \tilde{x})$ dan (x, t) gacha (1-rasm).

Keyin quyidagi munosabatni olamiz

$$p(x, t) + \sigma(x)w(x, t) - [p(\tilde{x}, t - x + \tilde{x}) + \sigma(\tilde{x})w(\tilde{x}, t - x + \tilde{x})] = \int_{\tilde{x}}^x [\sigma'(s)w(s, t - x + s) - \sigma(s)q(s)(w(s, t - x + s) - r(s, t - x + s))] ds. \quad (6)$$

1-rasm. (x, t) nuqtadan o'tuvchi belgilar.

Xuddi shunday, (5) tenglamani xarakteristikalar bo'ylab integrallash orqali $\frac{dt}{dx} = -1$ OT $(\tilde{x}, t + x - \tilde{x})$ gacha (x, t) (1-rasm), biz ikkinchi munosabatni olamiz:

$$p(x, t) - \sigma(x)w(x, t) - [p(\tilde{x}, t + x - \tilde{x}) - \sigma(\tilde{x})w(\tilde{x}, t + x - \tilde{x})] = - \int_{\tilde{x}}^x [\sigma'(s)w(s, t + x - s) + \sigma(s)q(s)(w(s, t + x - s) - r(s, t + x - s))] ds. \quad (7)$$

Olingan tenglamalar (6) va (7) allaqachon raqamli modellashtirish uchun mos keladi.

Keling, qo'ying $h = x - \tilde{x}$. $h > 0$ bo'lsin, lekin u etarlicha kichik. U holda integral ostidagi $\sigma'(s)$ ni ifoda orqali taxmin qilishimiz mumkin

$$\sigma'(s) \approx \frac{\sigma(x) - \sigma(\tilde{x})}{h}, \quad (8)$$

x va $\tilde{x}$ lar orasida joylashgan har qanday s uchun. (6) va (7) dan qolgan integratsiyani trapetsiya usulida yaqinlashtirgandan so'ng, taxminiy formulalarni olamiz. (9)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\tilde{x}}^x [\sigma'(s)w(s, t - x + s) - \sigma(s)q(s)(w(s, t - x + s) - r(s, t - x + s))] ds \approx \\ & \approx \frac{1}{2} [\sigma(x) - \sigma(\tilde{x})][w(x, t) + w(\tilde{x}, t - x + \tilde{x})] - \\ & \frac{h}{2} [\sigma(x)q(x)(w(x, t) - r(x, t)) + \sigma(\tilde{x})q(\tilde{x})(w(\tilde{x}, t - x + \tilde{x}) - r(\tilde{x}, t - x + \tilde{x}))], \end{aligned}$$

va mos ravishda quyidagicha yozish mumkin: (10)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\tilde{x}}^x [\sigma'(s)w(s, t + x - s) + \sigma(s)q(s)(w(s, t + x - s) - r(s, t + x - s))] ds \approx \\ & \approx \frac{1}{2} [\sigma(x) - \sigma(\tilde{x})][w(x, t) + w(\tilde{x}, t + x - \tilde{x})] + \\ & \frac{h}{2} [\sigma(x)q(x)(w(x, t) - r(x, t)) + \sigma(\tilde{x})q(\tilde{x})(w(\tilde{x}, t + x - \tilde{x}) - r(\tilde{x}, t + x - \tilde{x}))] \end{aligned}$$

Agar $\sigma(x)$ $s = x_0$ nuqtada uzilishga ega bo'lsa, bunda $\tilde{x} < x_0 < x$, lekin bu sirtida w maydoni uzluksiz, (9) va (10) tenglamalar yetarlicha kichik h uchun yaxshi yaqinlik beradi.

σ , q , p , w va r uchun panjara funksiyalari quyidagi munosabatlar bilan aniqlanadi:

$$\sigma_i = \sigma[(i - 1)h], \quad q_i = q[(i - 1)h], \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots,$$

bu yerda σ normallashtiriladi, shuning uchun $\sigma_1 = 1$,

$$p_{ij} = p[(i - 1)h, (2j - i - 1)h],$$

$$w_{ij} = w[(i - 1)h, (2j - i - 1)h]$$

$$r_{ij} = r[(i - 1)h, (2j - i - 1)h],$$

va $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, va $j \geq i$ uchun dastlabki shartlardan shuni olamiz

$$p_{ii} = w_{ii} = r_{ii} = 0, \text{ uchun } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \tag{11}$$

va chegara shartlaridan biz bor

$$p_{1i} = f_i = f[t = (j - 1)h], \quad w_{1i} = g'_i = g'[t = (j - 1)h], \tag{12}$$

2-rasm. Xarakteristikalar bo‘yicha integratsiya usulida qo‘llaniladigan raqamli panjara. Qalin chiziqlar giperbolik tenglamalar tizimining xarakteristikasidir (2). $x - t$ – chizig‘i - to‘lqinli front.

(6) va (7) tenglamalar (9) va (10) yaqinliklari bilan birgalikda inversiyaga mos keladi. Faraz qilaylik, σ_i $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, I$, uchun ma’lum, p_{ij} va w_{ij} esa barcha $i < I$ va $j > i$. uchun hisoblangan. U holda (6) va (7) tenglamalarni (9) va munosabatlarni hisobga olgan holda to‘rga proyeksiya qilish orqali olingan quyidagi munosabatlardan $p_{I,j}$ va $w_{I,j}$ ni ifodalashimiz mumkin (10):

$$p_{I,j} + \sigma_I w_{I,j} = p_{I-1,j-1} + \sigma_{I-1} w_{I-1,j-1} + \frac{1}{2} [\sigma_I - \sigma_{I-1}] [w_{I,j} + w_{I-1,j-1}] -$$

$$= -\frac{h}{2} [\sigma_I q_I (w_{I,j} - r_{I,j}) + \sigma_{I-1} q_{I-1} (w_{I-1,j-1} - r_{I-1,j-1})] \tag{13}$$

$$p_{I,j} - \sigma_I w_{I,j} = p_{I-1,j} - \sigma_{I-1} w_{I-1,j} - \frac{1}{2} [\sigma_I - \sigma_{I-1}] [w_{I,j} + w_{I-1,j}] -$$

$$= -\frac{h}{2} [\sigma_I q_I (w_{I,j} - r_{I,j}) + \sigma_{I-1} q_{I-1} (w_{I-1,j} - r_{I-1,j-1})] \tag{14}$$

uchun $j = I + 1, I + 2, \dots$.

Bu tenglamalarni $p_{I,j}$ va $w_{I,j}$ uchun yechamiz. $\sigma(x) > 0$ bo‘lgani uchun $\sigma_{I-1} + \sigma_I > 0$ bo‘ladi. Biz olamiz:

$$p_{l,j} = \frac{1}{2}(p_{l-1,j-1} + p_{l-1,j}) + \frac{1}{4}(\sigma_{l-1} + \sigma_l)(w_{l-1,j-1} - w_{l-1,j}) - \frac{h}{2}\sigma_l q_l (w_{l,j} - r_{l,j}) - \frac{h}{4}\sigma_{l-1} q_{l-1} [(w_{l-1,j-1} - r_{l-1,j-1}) + (w_{l-1,j} - r_{l-1,j})], \quad (15)$$

$$w_{l,j} = \frac{(p_{l-1,j-1} - p_{l-1,j})}{\sigma_{l-1} + \sigma_l} + \frac{1}{2}(w_{l-1,j-1} + w_{l-1,j}) - \frac{\frac{h}{2}\sigma_{l-1} q_{l-1} [(w_{l-1,j-1} - r_{l-1,j-1}) - (w_{l-1,j} - r_{l-1,j})]}{\sigma_{l-1} + \sigma_l}. \quad (16)$$

Xususan, $p_{l,l+1}$ va $w_{l,l+1}$ hisoblanadi.

Endi $\rho_l(z)V_{tt} = \chi(z)\rho_l^2(z)(U_t - V_t)$ tenglamaga qaytaylik. Uning o'ng va chap tomonlarini $\rho_l(z)$ ga bo'lib, biz uni t vaqt ichida integrallash mumkinligini ta'kidlaymiz. Dastlabki shartlarni $U|_{t=0} = 0$; $U_t|_{t=0} = 0$ va $V|_{t=0} = 0$; $V_t|_{t=0} = 0$ hisobga olgan holda, biz quyidagilarni olamiz:

$$V_t = \chi(x)\rho_l(x)(U - V) \quad (17)$$

Ushbu tenglamani rasmda ko'rsatilgan bir xil tarmoqqa proyeksiya qilish. 3.6.2 va birinchi marta v_t hosilasini birinchi farqga yaqinlashtirish

$$V_t(t, x) \approx \frac{V(t + 2h, x) - V(t, x)}{2h}$$

olamiz:

$$r_{ij} = (\chi\rho_l)_i(U_{ij} - V_{ij}), \quad r_{ij+1} = (\chi\rho_l)_i(U_{ij+1} - V_{ij+1}) \quad (18)$$

Birinchi tenglamani ikkinchisidan ayirib, biz quyidagilarni olamiz:

$$r_{ij+1} - r_{ij} = (\chi\rho_l)_i((U_{ij+1} - U_{ij}) - (V_{ij+1} - V_{ij}))$$

Endi birinchi farqdan foydalanib, xuddi shunday u_t ga yaqinlashishi

$$w_{ij} = (U_t)_{ij} = \frac{U_{ij+1} - U_{ij}}{2h}$$

bizda ... bor:

$$r_{ij+1} = r_{ij} + 2h(\chi\rho_l)_i(w_{ij} - r_{ij}) \quad (19)$$

(14) tenglamaga I o'rniga $i+1$ ni va (13) tenglamaga I o'rniga i ni qo'yib, p_{ij} va w_{ij} uchun hosil bo'lgan munosabatlarni yechib, quyidagi munosabatlarga erishamiz. (14) tenglamaga I o'rniga $i+1$ ni va (13) tenglamaga I o'rniga i ni qo'yib, p_{ij} va w_{ij} uchun hosil bo'lgan munosabatlarni yechib, quyidagi munosabatlarga erishamiz.

$$w_{ij} = \frac{1}{\Delta} \{ 2(p_{i-1,j-1} - p_{i-1,j}) + (\sigma_i + \sigma_{i-1})w_{i-1,j-1} + (\sigma_{i+1} + \sigma_i)w_{i+1,j} \} - \frac{1}{\Delta} \{ h[\sigma_{i+1}q_{i+1}(w_{i+1,j} - r_{i+1,j}) - 2\sigma_i q_i r_{ij} + \sigma_{i-1}q_{i-1}(w_{i-1,j-1} - r_{i-1,j-1})] \}, \quad (20)$$

$$p_{ij} = p_{i-1,j-1} - \frac{1}{2} [\sigma_i + \sigma_{i-1}]w_{i,j} + \frac{1}{2} [\sigma_i + \sigma_{i-1}]w_{i-1,j-1} - \frac{h}{2} [\sigma_i q_i (w_{i,j} - r_{i,j}) + \sigma_{i-1} q_{i-1} (w_{i-1,j-1} - r_{i-1,j-1})], \quad (21)$$

bu yerda $\Delta = \sigma_{i+1} + 2\sigma_i + \sigma_{i-1} + 2h\sigma_i q_i$. $I = 2$ ni (15) va (16) ga almashtirish va u yerdan $p_{1,j-1}$, $w_{1,j-1}$ va $r_{1,j-1}$ ni chiqarib tashlash, shuningdek, olish $\sigma_1 = 1$ ekanligini hisobga olsak, biz munosabatni olamiz

$$w_{1,j} = w_{2,j} \frac{1 + \sigma_2 - h\sigma_2 q_2}{1 + \sigma_2 + hq_1} + \frac{2(p_{1,j} - p_{2,j}) + hq_1 r_{1,j} + h\sigma_2 q_2 r_{2,j}}{1 + \sigma_2 + hq_1} \quad (22)$$

uning yordamida (18) munosabat bilan birgalikda $\rho_s(z)U_{tt} = (\mu(z)U_z)_z - \chi(z)\rho_l^2(z)(U_t - V_t) \mu U_z|_{z=0} = F(t)$ to'g'ridan-to'g'ri masalani yechish sxemasini olamiz.

Ta'rif bo'yicha biz taklif qilamiz $p_{0,j} = w_{0,j} = r_{0,j} = 0$. (16) formuladan topamiz $w_{1,2} = 0$, va (11) va (19) formulalardan $r_{1,2} = 0$ kelib chiqadi.

Xuddi shunday $w_{1,j} = 0$ va $r_{1,j} = 0$ $j = 3, 4, \dots$ uchun hisoblanadi. Keyinchalik, $j = 2, 3, 4, \dots$ uchun $p_{i,j}$, $w_{i,j}$, $r_{i,j}$ panjara funksiyalarining qiymatlari hisoblanadi.

NATIJALAR. Dastlabki chegaraviy muammoni

$$\rho_s u_{tt} = (\mu(u_x)u_x)_x - \rho_l^2 \left((u-v)\chi(u-v) \right)_t, \quad x \in (0, L), t \in (0, T),$$

$$\rho_s u_{tt} = (\mu(u_x)u_x)_x - \rho_l^2 \left((u-v)\chi(u-v) \right)_t, \quad x \in (0, L), t \in (0, T),$$

$\rho_s u_{tt} = (\mu(u_x)u_x)_x - \rho_l^2((u-v)\chi(u-v))_t$, $x \in (0, L), t \in (0, T)$,
 $u|_{x=0} = 0$, $\mu(u_x)u_x|_{x=L} = f(t)$, $t \in (0, T)$ sonli yechish uchun biz vaqt (τ)
va fazo (h) bo'yicha tegishli diskretizatsiya bosqichlari bilan yaqinlashuvning
ikkinchi tartibiga ega bo'lgan aniq farq sxemasidan foydalanamiz:

$$\frac{1}{\tau^2} (u_j^{i+1} - 2u_j^i + u_j^{i-1}) = \frac{1}{2h^2 \rho_s} ((\mu_{j+1}^{i-1} + \mu_j^{i-1})(u_{j+1}^i - u_j^i) -$$

$$-(\mu_j^{i-1} + \mu_{j-1}^{i-1})(u_j^i - u_{j-1}^i)) - \frac{1}{\tau \rho_s} \rho_l^2 ((u_j^i - v_j^i)\chi_j^i - (u_j^{i-1} - v_j^{i-1})\chi_j^{i-1})$$

$$v_j^{i+1} = \rho_l \tau (u_j^{i+1} - v_j^{i+1})\chi_j^i + v_j^i \quad i = 0, \dots, N, \quad j = 0, \dots, M$$

boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlarni yaqinlashtirish bilan shug'ullanamiz.

$$u_j^0, \frac{u_j^1 - u_j^0}{\tau} = \sin(jh), \quad v_j^0 = 0, \quad j = 0, \dots, M \quad u_0^i = 0, \quad u_M^i = 0,$$

$$i = 0, \dots, N$$

MUHOKAMA. Biz Kurant raqamini 0,5 dan kichik deb hisoblaymiz, bu foydalanilgan farq sxemasining barqarorligini ta'minlaydi.

Model sifatida biz assimilyatsiya qiluvchi bir hil g'ovak qatlamdan iborat muhitni o'rnatamiz. Keling, qatlamning quyidagi fizik xususiyatlarini faraz qilaylik:

Model sifatida biz assimilyatsiya qiluvchi bir xil g'ovak qatlamdan iborat muhitni o'rnatamiz. Keling, qatlamning quyidagi fizik xususiyatlarini faraz qilaylik:

$$\rho_s^f = 1,5 \text{ g/sm}^3, \quad \rho_l^f = 1 \text{ g/sm}^3, \quad c_s = 1,3 \text{ km/sek}, \quad d = 0,1,$$

$\chi = 1000 \frac{\text{sm}^3}{\text{g}} * \text{sek}$, berilgan funktsiyalar $u_0(x) = 0$, $u_1(x) = \sin x$, Manbadagi vaqt signali Puzyrev impulsi shaklida aniqlangan:

$$f(t) = \exp\left(-\frac{2\pi f_0(t-t_0)^2}{\gamma^2}\right) \sin(2\pi f_0(t-t_0)), \text{ bu yerda } \gamma = 4, f_0 = 1 \text{ Gts},$$

$t_0 = 1,5 \text{ sek}$. U siljish tezligi u uchun to'liq in maydonining seysmik izini ko'rsatadi. Rasmdan ko'rinib turibdiki, to'liq in masofaga qarab susayadi.

XULOSA. Ko'rib chiqilayotgan chiziqli bo'lmagan to'g'ridan-to'g'ri dinamik muammoning g'ovakli muhit uchun to'g'riligi funktsional tahlil usullari asosida ko'rsatilgan. G'ovak - elastik muhitda ko'ndalang to'liqlar tenglamasi uchun

to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri dinamik masalaning yagona yechimi qurilgan.

G‘ovak - elastik muhitda ko‘ndalang to‘lqinlar tenglamasi uchun bir o‘lchovli dinamik masalalar uchun ikkinchi turdagi chiziqli Volterra integral tenglamalari tizimi olinadi. Bu sistemadan ko‘rib chiqilayotgan to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri masalalar yechimlarining mavjudligi va yagonaligi teoremasi kelib chiqadi.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI (REFERENCES)

[1] Доровский В.Н. Континуальная теория фильтрации // Геология и геофизика. - 1989. - № 7. - С. 39-45.

[2] Доровский В.Н. Уравнения континуальной теории фильтрации. Новосибирск, 1987, 9с. (Препр / ИГиГ СО АН СССР, №9).

[3] Романов В.Г. Обратные задачи математической физики. М.: Наука, 1984. -263 с.

[4] Холмуродов А.Э. Численное решение одномерных прямых задач распространения поперечных волн в пористых средах// Научный журнал “Проблемы вычислительной и прикладной математики”, ТУИТ, № 1(3) 2018, С. 42-48. (05.00.00, №23)

[5] Xolmurodov, A., Muhammad, M., & Quzratov, M. (2024). G‘OVAK MUHITNING TO‘G‘RI CHIZIQLI DINAMIK MASALASINI BAYON QILISH VA YECHISH. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, 2(2), 26-30.

[6] Xolmurodov, A., Matanov, M., & Quzratov, M. (2024, November). Propagation of harmonic plane waves in an elastic half-space. Field equations. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 3244, No. 1). AIP Publishing.